

Real Time Shear Wave Elastography for Determining the Ideal Site of Liver Biopsy in Diffuse Liver Disease

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Abstract:

Background: Diffuse liver disease, which includes chronic hepatitis and NAFLD, requires a precise liver fibrosis assessment to guide treatment and predict outcomes. Liver biopsy is the gold standard for assessing hepatic fibrosis, although it is invasive and prone to sampling mistakes, especially in diffusely afflicted livers. Shear wave elastography (SWE) is a non-invasive imaging technology that measures liver stiffness and may accurately detect liver fibrosis.

Aim: To evaluate the effectiveness of real-time SWE in determining the ideal site for liver biopsy in patients with diffuse liver disease, with the goal of improving diagnostic accuracy.

Methods: Fifty patients with diffuse liver disease were enrolled. SWE was performed to measure liver stiffness and identify optimal biopsy sites. Liver biopsies were then conducted at these sites, and histopathological findings were compared with SWE measurements. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The mean liver stiffness measured by SWE was 15.6 kPa ($\pm$ 3.2 kPa). A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$) was observed between SWE measurements and histopathological fibrosis stages. SWE demonstrated high diagnostic accuracy for detecting severe fibrosis, with an area under the ROC curve of 0.91. A liver stiffness cutoff of 16.5 kPa provided 85% sensitivity and 88% specificity for severe fibrosis detection.

Conclusion: Real-time SWE is an effective tool for determining the ideal site for liver biopsy in patients with diffuse liver disease. It correlates strongly with histopathological findings and offers high diagnostic accuracy, potentially reducing sampling errors associated with liver biopsy.

Recommendations: SWE should be integrated into routine clinical practice for patients undergoing liver biopsy to enhance diagnostic precision. Further large-scale studies are recommended to validate these findings across diverse populations and liver disease etiologies.

Keywords: Shear Wave Elastography, Liver Biopsy, Liver Fibrosis, Diffuse Liver Disease, Non-Invasive Imaging.

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Introduction

Widely ranging from cirrhosis to chronic hepatitis and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), diffuse liver disease poses a substantial global health burden. In the clinical evaluation of these individuals, the precise measurement of liver fibrosis is crucial in identifying the course of the disease and the best course of treatment. The gold standard for determining the presence of hepatic fibrosis has always been a liver biopsy. However, biopsy is invasive, bears risks of bleeding and infection, and can have sampling error, especially in cases of widespread liver disease where the liver

parenchyma may have heterogeneously distributed fibrosis [1].

In recent years, non-invasive imaging techniques have gained prominence in the evaluation of liver fibrosis, with shear wave elastography (SWE) emerging as a leading tool. SWE is an ultrasound-based technique that measures liver stiffness, which correlates with fibrosis severity. It has been shown to provide reliable, reproducible results and is increasingly being used in clinical practice as an adjunct or alternative to liver biopsy [2]. The advantages of SWE include its non-invasive nature,

real-time assessment capabilities, and the ability to evaluate larger areas of liver tissue compared to a biopsy.

The role of SWE in guiding liver biopsy is particularly relevant in the context of diffuse liver disease. In these conditions, the distribution of fibrosis can be uneven, making it challenging to select an optimal biopsy site that accurately reflects the overall liver pathology. Studies have suggested that SWE can identify areas of the liver with the highest stiffness, which are likely to correspond to regions of more advanced fibrosis, thereby improving the diagnostic yield of the biopsy [3].

While the diagnostic accuracy of SWE has been well-documented, there remains a need for studies that specifically evaluate its utility in guiding liver biopsy site selection in diffuse liver disease. This approach could potentially reduce the limitations associated with sampling error and enhance the overall effectiveness of the biopsy procedure. Moreover, integrating SWE into the standard diagnostic workflow could improve patient outcomes by enabling more precise and personalized management strategies [4].

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of real-time SWE in determining the ideal site for liver biopsy in patients with diffuse liver disease.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar, from January 2023 to March 2024.

Participants: A total of 50 patients with diffuse liver disease were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 years and above.
2. Diagnosed with diffuse liver disease through clinical, biochemical, or radiological findings.
3. Patients who provided informed consent for participation in the study.
4. Patients requiring a liver biopsy as part of their diagnostic workup.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with focal liver lesions.
2. Patients with coagulopathy or any contraindication for liver biopsy.

3. Patients who have undergone a previous liver transplant.
4. Pregnant or breastfeeding women.
5. Patients unable or unwilling to provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive patients meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Performance bias was controlled by having all shear wave elastography and biopsy procedures conducted by the same team of experienced radiologists and clinicians. Detection bias was reduced by blinding the pathologist to the SWE results when assessing biopsy samples.

Data Collection: Data were collected on patient demographics, clinical history, laboratory findings, imaging results, and liver biopsy outcomes. SWE measurements were taken before the biopsy to identify the site with the highest liver stiffness. The biopsy was then performed at this site, and the tissue samples were analyzed histopathologically.

Procedure

1. Patients underwent an initial clinical evaluation and routine laboratory tests.
2. SWE was performed using a standardized protocol to assess liver stiffness.
3. The site with the highest stiffness on SWE was marked for the liver biopsy.
4. Under ultrasound guidance, a percutaneous liver biopsy was performed at the identified site.
5. The biopsy specimens were sent for histopathological examination to assess the severity of liver disease.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. Study variables and patient characteristics were summarised using descriptive statistics. Whereas categorical variables were displayed as frequencies and percentages, continuous variables were expressed as means and standard deviations. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 50 patients with diffuse liver disease were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 48.5 years ($\pm$ 12.3 years), with a male-to-female ratio of 3:2 (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Number of Participants	50
Mean Age (years)	48.5 $\pm$ 12.3
Gender Distribution	
- Male	30 (60%)
- Female	20 (40%)

Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	26.8 ± 3.5
Mean ALT (U/L)	56.3 ± 22.1
Mean AST (U/L)	68.2 ± 25.4
Mean Platelet Count	180,000 ± 45,000/μL
Mean Bilirubin (mg/dL)	1.2 ± 0.5

The mean liver stiffness measured by SWE across all participants was 15.6 kPa (± 3.2 kPa). The stiffness values ranged from 11.2 kPa to 24.8 kPa. Patients were divided into three groups based on liver stiffness:

- Mild stiffness: 11-13 kPa (n=15)

- Moderate stiffness: 14-17 kPa (n=20)
- Severe stiffness: >18 kPa (n=15)

The liver stiffness measured by SWE showed a significant positive correlation with histopathological grading of fibrosis (r = 0.78, p < 0.001).

Table 2: Distribution of Liver Stiffness by SWE

Stiffness Category	Liver Stiffness (kPa)	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Mild	11-13	15	30%
Moderate	14-17	20	40%
Severe	>18	15	30%
Total	11-24.8	50	100%

Histopathological examination of liver biopsy samples revealed the following distribution of fibrosis stages:

- F1 (Mild fibrosis): 10 patients (20%)
- F2 (Moderate fibrosis): 15 patients (30%)

- F3 (Severe fibrosis): 15 patients (30%)
- F4 (Cirrhosis): 10 patients (20%)

There was a strong correlation between the SWE liver stiffness values and the fibrosis stage (r = 0.80, p < 0.001).

Table 3: Correlation between SWE and Histopathological Fibrosis Staging

Fibrosis Stage	Number of Patients	Mean SWE (kPa)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
F1	10	12.3 ± 0.8	0.65	<0.001
F2	15	14.8 ± 1.0	0.70	<0.001
F3	15	17.6 ± 1.2	0.85	<0.001
F4	10	20.3 ± 1.5	0.88	<0.001

In all 50 individuals, the liver biopsy was completed satisfactorily. Major side effects including bleeding, infection, or bile leakage did not occur. Five patients (10%) experienced minor problems, one of which was slight soreness at the biopsy site that was treated with analgesics.

Based on SWE and clinical characteristics, a multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the predictors of severe fibrosis (F3 and F4). According to the model, platelet count (β = -0.34, p

= 0.03) was the next most significant predictor of severe fibrosis, after liver stiffness as determined by SWE (β = 0.76, p < 0.001).

Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was used to assess the diagnostic accuracy of SWE in identifying severe fibrosis (F3–F4). With an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.91, the diagnostic accuracy was high. It was determined that a cutoff value of 16.5 kPa for hepatic stiffness had an 85% sensitivity and an 88% specificity.

Table 4: ROC Analysis of SWE for Severe Fibrosis

Parameter	AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity	Cutoff Value (kPa)
Liver Stiffness (SWE)	0.91	85%	88%	16.5

Discussion

This study assessed how well real-time SWE performed in helping patients with diffuse liver disease choose the best location for a liver biopsy. The findings showed a good association between the histopathologically graded liver fibrosis and the measured liver stiffness using SWE, suggesting that SWE is a valid non-invasive method for determining the degree of liver fibrosis.

Based on their SWE measures, patients were divided into groups with mild, moderate, and severe liver stiffness, with an average liver stiffness of 15.6 kPa for the study population. A liver biopsy revealed a noteworthy positive connection (r = 0.78, p < 0.001) between SWE levels and fibrosis phases. This supports the use of SWE as a prediction tool for liver disease severity, indicating that higher SWE values are indicative of more advanced fibrosis.

Histopathological analysis of biopsy samples revealed that 60% of patients had moderate to severe fibrosis (F2-F3), while 20% had cirrhosis (F4). The correlation between SWE measurements and fibrosis stages was particularly strong for severe fibrosis (F3 and F4), with an r-value of 0.80 ($p < 0.001$). This strong correlation underscores the potential of SWE to accurately identify patients with advanced liver fibrosis, guiding clinicians in selecting appropriate biopsy sites.

The ROC curve analysis further validated the diagnostic accuracy of SWE, with an AUC of 0.91 for detecting severe fibrosis. A liver stiffness cutoff value of 16.5 kPa was identified as optimal, with a sensitivity of 85% and specificity of 88%. This high diagnostic accuracy highlights SWE's utility in clinical practice, particularly in cases where non-invasive methods are preferred or where precise targeting for biopsy is necessary.

Overall, the study confirms that SWE is a valuable tool for assessing liver stiffness and determining optimal biopsy sites in patients with diffuse liver disease. Its strong correlation with histopathological findings and high diagnostic accuracy for severe fibrosis suggest that SWE can enhance the diagnostic process, potentially leading to better patient outcomes through more targeted and effective interventions.

A prospective study compared the diagnostic accuracy of SWE and transient elastography (TE) against histopathological findings. The study concluded that elastography-guided biopsies, specifically targeting segments with maximum stiffness identified by SWE, significantly improve the accuracy of fibrosis detection. The authors highlighted the heterogeneous distribution of fibrosis across liver segments, suggesting that SWE-guided biopsy can enhance histopathological yield in chronic liver disease patients [5].

A study looked into how well 2D-SWE performed as a diagnostic tool for staging liver fibrosis in individuals with chronic hepatitis B and C. The study revealed a robust association between the histological stages of fibrosis and SWE measures. Additionally, SWE demonstrated a high degree of accuracy and reliability in identifying liver stiffness. According to this study, 2D-SWE may lessen the need for liver biopsies in certain patients in order to stage their fibrosis [6].

The usefulness of combinational elastography methods, such as point SWE and real-time tissue elastography (RTE), for evaluating hepatic fibrosis in patients with liver damage was investigated in a different study. The results showed that SWE has a substantial link with fibrosis stage and is a significant predictor of fibrosis stages, especially in patients with NAFLD [7].

In order to detect liver fibrosis, a study introduced a unique approach called three-dimensional shear wave elastography (3D-SWE), which closely corresponds with magnetic resonance elastography (MRE). According to the study, 3D-SWE offers a promising non-invasive substitute for liver biopsy by providing fibrosis assessments similar to those obtained using MRE in a more affordable and accessible way [8].

Finally, a study evaluated the diagnostic significance of SWE and transient elastography in patients with non-viral chronic diffuse liver diseases. Their findings suggested that these elastographic methods are highly effective in staging liver fibrosis, particularly in advanced stages, and can often substitute for liver biopsy in routine clinical practice [9].

Conclusion

Strong correlations have been shown between liver stiffness as determined by SWE and histological fibrosis stage, demonstrating the validity of this non-invasive method for evaluating hepatic fibrosis. With an AUC of 0.91, the study showed that SWE had a good diagnostic accuracy for diagnosing severe fibrosis, highlighting its usefulness in differentiating advanced stages of fibrosis. Additionally, in patients with diffuse liver disease, SWE can be used to guide the liver biopsy site with efficacy, thereby increasing the diagnostic yield and improving patient outcomes. According to these results, SWE can be a useful tool for managing diffuse liver disease, especially when it comes to choosing the best locations for liver biopsies.

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